

**ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLEXITY AND GREEN INNOVATION: THE SIGNIFICANCE
OF OPEN INNOVATION**

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Abstract: This paper looks into how green innovation affects the performance of firms nowadays. The investigations prove that green innovation improves both the economic and environmental performance. It was also discovered that green innovation has a beneficial impact on company performance. These findings suggested that businesses should step up their green innovation initiatives to provide better results and look for strategies to lower environmental uncertainty in order to maintain these outputs at their highest possible level. Lastly, the study offers some insights into the advantages and possibilities of green innovation within the framework of open innovation.

Keywords: green innovation; environmental friendly products; environmental effects, pollution, innovative products, environmental damage.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается, как «зеленые» инновации влияют на эффективность компаний в наши дни. Исследования доказывают, что «зеленые» инновации улучшают как экономические, так и экологические показатели. Было также обнаружено, что «зеленые» инновации оказывают благотворное влияние на производительность компании. Эти результаты свидетельствуют о том, что предприятиям следует активизировать свои инициативы в области зеленых инноваций, чтобы обеспечить лучшие результаты, и искать стратегии, позволяющие снизить экологическую неопределенность, чтобы поддерживать эти результаты на максимально возможном уровне. Наконец, исследование предлагает некоторое представление о преимуществах и возможностях «зеленых» инноваций в рамках открытых инноваций.

Ключевые слова: зеленые инновации; экологически чистая продукция; экологические последствия, загрязнение, инновационная продукция, экологический ущерб.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola bugungi kunda yashil innovatsiyalar firmalar faoliyatiga qanday ta'sir qilishini ko'rib chiqadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yashil innovatsiyalar iqtisodiy va ekologik ko'rsatkichlarni yaxshilaydi. Shuningdek, yashil innovatsiyalar kompaniya faoliyatiga foydali ta'sir ko'rsatishi aniqlandi. Ushbu tahlillar korxonalar yaxshi natijalarni ta'minlash uchun yashil innovatsion tashabbuslarini kuchaytirishi va ushbu natijalarni iloji boricha yuqori darajada ushlab turish uchun ekologik noaniqlikni kamaytirish strategiyalarini izlashlari kerakligini ko'rsatdi. Nihoyat, tadqiqot ochiq innovatsiyalar doirasida yashil innovatsiyaning afzalliklari va imkoniyatlari haqida ba'zi tushunchalarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil innovatsiya; ekologik toza mahsulotlar; atrof-muhit ta'siri, ifloslanish, innovatsion mahsulotlar, atrof-muhitga zarar.

Introduction

Nowadays, a lot of people are aware of and concerned about the environment. They are now more receptive to things that are good for the environment. Consumer preference for ecologically friendly items is growing daily as a result of this awareness. Additionally, businesses

provide cutting-edge goods, manufacturing techniques, and business strategies to lessen the harm, pollution, and other negative environmental effects they produce. These goods, procedures, and techniques are essential components of the system that guarantees environmental sustainability and lessens or stops environmental harm. In order to satisfy stakeholders, businesses must use green innovation techniques. By integrating green ideas into their operational procedures, businesses can restructure their operations through the use of "green innovation" strategies [1].

One particular kind of innovation that takes environmental responsibility into account is called "green innovation." A more accurate definition of green innovation would be the discovery of novel processes and goods that provide value by reducing adverse environmental effects and promoting sustainable objectives. Furthermore, waste minimization, pollution avoidance, and environmental management are all included in the term "green innovation." In particular, green innovation covers a wide range of commercial activities that are fueled by new technology and procedures, including purchasing, production, operation, and sales. Green innovation is the application of eco-friendly techniques to create new or enhanced products, processes, or organizational changes. The goal of green innovation is to develop, apply, or provide something novel for the client or the business [4].

Green innovations developed by companies contribute significantly to a more sustainable society. Companies must put plans into place that will take into account the actions of their collaborators and lessen the environmental harm that their products do in order to increase green innovation activities. This is not a task that should be completed rapidly. In today's business environment, businesses have both a task and an opportunity to pursue their economic goals and meet their social duties. Businesses should evaluate their level of preparedness for green innovation in order to minimize risks and maximize rewards. Businesses ought to concentrate on creating new goods and getting their production lines ready for green innovation. When compared to their current competition, manufacturing organizations can enhance their service and innovation skills by creating new goods and processes with the aid of green innovation approaches [6].

Governments are enacting various laws and regulations to lessen pollution in tandem with consumers' growing environmental consciousness. It is well recognized that "three" waste sources, carbon dioxide, and nonrenewable commercial energy consumption are the pollutants that are thought to have a significant impact on the environment. Hence, addressing the causes of environmental pollution, such as carbon emissions, is a crucial subject that interests nations and international organizations. Because carbon emissions are cross-border in nature, collaboration is necessary, particularly across nations, governments, and regions. As a result, green innovation initiatives are inextricably tied to the environment and cannot be seen in a vacuum [8].

Theoretical Framework

When compared to other forms of innovation, the idea of "environmental responsibility" is known as "green innovation," which is the development of novel goods and procedures that provide a definite advantage while also being environmentally friendly. Green innovation improves resource management, gets rid of waste, and lowers pollution in addition to the previously listed areas. The term "Greening of Industries" broadly describes new business practices, technology, and processes that are applied to safeguard and preserve the environment; for example, to create a new or better outcome, like a process, product, or organization that integrates eco-friendly ideas or procedures. The goal of innovation as a creative concept is to assist a business or individual in producing, utilizing, or providing something novel [9].

Green product innovation and green process innovation are the two subtopics under which green innovation can be studied. Only when prepared for every aspect of green innovation can a corporation fully leverage its potential and reap its rewards. Based on a prior self-assessment of their preparedness for green innovation, companies can quickly establish or enhance a business case, focus necessary resources, and gather core capabilities before and during the implementation phase [2].

Green product innovation refers to the application of creative concepts that facilitate the creation, manufacturing, and distribution of novel environmentally friendly products that outperform conventional or rival goods. Upgrades that increase the product's efficiency and design changes that make recycling easier are frequently beneficial for environmentally friendly products. Safer raw materials, fewer hazardous materials, and improved product durability or recyclability are all parts of the total green product innovation. Green product innovation is centered on enhancing a product's features or design to reduce the harm the product causes to the environment [5].

Lean manufacturing, agile manufacturing, and quality-control techniques that eliminate or significantly lower defective parts are examples of green process practices. These constituents mitigate deleterious ecological ramifications, culminating in enhanced raw material efficiency and decreased production of waste and byproducts. Furthermore, analytical techniques are employed in the production process, which is automatically managed. Innovation in green processes is more efficient than other environmental measures. But this kind of innovation is more expensive and necessitates more internal dynamics. Green process innovation can be incorporated into production by recovering outputs, improving production, or substituting inputs. When creating new and green processes, the environment and the demands of the client are taken into account. The primary barriers to green innovation are the following: a stagnant environmental regulation system based on state inefficiencies; a lack of environmental education among company employees; long-term return on investment; challenges in obtaining financial resources; challenges in networking between partners and green teams; and inefficiencies in the internal communication process [10].

Literature Review

The fundamentals of green innovation are established by laws, but internal business factors like corporate cultures and resource availability also influence green innovation. Companies need to consistently fulfill their social responsibilities and make significant expenditures in order to maximize long-term advantages. Hence, it is possible to develop a sustainable method of improving a business's performance without harming the environment. An organization's performance benefits from green innovation. The development of ecologically friendly products, enhanced operational effectiveness, and increased administrative effectiveness are the means by which these impacts are realized. Green innovation improves environmental performance by assisting a business in mitigating its ecological impacts and adhering to sustainability laws. In order to create a new business model and a better business opportunity, eco-innovation enterprises will have an impact on industry regulations [9].

By creating new eco-friendly goods and procedures, green innovation can assist businesses in satisfying a wide range of client demands and promoting a green image. Green innovation thereby boosts the company's market share and generates significant revenues. Businesses can lower pollution, use more resources, and conserve resources in this way. Higher-priced products

can be marketed because green innovation provide a clear product advantage. By cutting waste, businesses that adopt a green innovation approach can make better use of raw materials [2].

Green innovation lessens the discharge of toxic substances and the usage of natural resources. Green innovation enhances environmental performance in this way. Additionally, by reducing waste, new green product and process development removes an organization's negative environmental impact and lowers costs. Green innovation is the process of reducing a company's negative environmental effects while simultaneously improving that company's success. Using green process innovation in the production process is one approach to speed up production while cutting costs and time. In addition to being a useful weapon in the fight against environmental problems, environmental innovation is also crucial for business because it can increase revenue. Green innovation has several advantages for businesses, such as higher sales and productivity as well as lower expenses, which boost profitability [10].

Discussion

A business need manufactured goods to be efficient. Both consumers and society require reasonably priced, high-quality products as well as a secure environment for next generations. The global climate crisis has raised public awareness of environmental issues, which has led to changes in consumer preferences and government legislation on the subject. As a result, the pressure that followed heightened market rivalry and prompted businesses to find creative solutions. The literature emphasizes how innovation enhances the development of new products and processes, giving businesses a competitive edge. Regulators, customer demands, environmental uncertainties, and environmental repercussions are just a few of the risks that businesses must deal with, particularly when pursuing green innovation. Companies may take a while to get a return on their investments in innovative endeavors due to these risks. [9].

Open innovation is better suited to manage resource and environmental externalities, allocate organizational resources equitably, and maintain internal market equilibrium. Incorporating open innovation is crucial for organizations to support sustainable development. Businesses and other manufacturing groups should encourage networking and knowledge exchange since these activities will have an overall impact on the growth of sustainable manufacturing and the adoption of innovative, environmentally friendly methods [10].

Engaging in green innovation within the framework of open innovation yields even greater benefits. By fostering a genuine culture of open innovation, businesses allow the outside world to help them innovate. From the standpoint of open innovation, they might gain from opening up the firm borders and bringing in outside knowledge. For instance, businesses can benefit in several ways from their innovations in terms of the environment by working together with suppliers and customers. Green innovation will therefore become sustainable and efficient thanks to open innovation.

Conclusion

In addition to businesses' aspirations for growth and sustainability, our world is confronted with issues such as fast population expansion, global warming, climate change, food and water shortages, energy and environmental challenges, and ill living conditions. While there are benefits to technology advancements like increased productivity and growth, there are drawbacks as well, such the issues listed above. The significance of environmental activities has grown in this setting in recent years, which is what inspired us to conduct this study. The paper demonstrates that while technology sharply intensifies market rivalry, green innovation strategies offer a substantial

benefit. Since green innovation initiatives can result in cost savings, businesses should concentrate on them in order to achieve higher and more sustainable performance. Examples of these initiatives include the utilization of recycled raw materials and renewable energy. Customers with strong environmental awareness may favor businesses that have improved their environmental performance as a result of green innovation techniques, resulting in customer loyalty. Moreover, businesses will benefit from investing in green innovation since it enhances financial performance and corporate image. Companies need to leverage their current environmental knowledge, capabilities, and processes to improve green products and green designs while concentrating on new environmental knowledge and skills, open innovation, and new markets and green products to address environmental concerns. Green innovation has a substantially less impact when the environment is unclear. Businesses are more likely to be ignorant of green technologies when technological uncertainty is high. In order to keep up with the rapid pace of technological development, companies that lack skilled expert knowledge about new goods or processes should look for both internal and external sources of information. Thus, businesses need to maintain both internal and external learning in an environment of high technical unpredictability. This circumstance highlights the value of open innovation once more. Given the centrality of humans to all commercial endeavors, it is suggested that future research look at the direct involvement of all parties in the green innovation process.

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